

Interaction of Charcoal with Chlorine Water : Part III. Simultaneous Chemisorption of Oxygen and Chlorine

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Interaction of charcoal with aqueous chlorine results in chemisorption of oxygen as well as chlorine, the magnitude of the former increasing and that of the latter decreasing on evacuating charcoal at increasing temperatures. It appears that while chlorine is fixed partly in replacement of combined hydrogen present on the charcoal surface and partly by addition at the unsaturated sites, oxygen is fixed partly at certain active centres where two oxygen atoms can be attached per active surface carbon atom giving rise to acidic CO₂-complex and partly at the unsaturated sites in competition with chlorine.

It was reported in previous publications ^{1,2} that interaction of charcoal with chlorine water involves conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid, in the earlier stages, and into chloric acid in latter stages, together with chemisorption of oxygen by the charcoal leading to the formation of carbon-oxygen surface complexes. The possibility of simultaneous chemisorption of chlorine during the interaction was not explored. In view of recent findings from our laboratories³ as well as from elsewhere ^{4,5} that interaction of charcoal or carbon black with gaseous chlorine at 100° or above results in chemisorption of chlorine leading to formation of carbon-chlorine surface complexes, it was thought of interest to investigate if chlorine is also chemisorbed along with oxygen during the treatment of charcoal with aqueous chlorine. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : Sugar and coconut charcoals prepared by the usual methods⁶ were exposed to oxygen at atmospheric pressure for 3 days and were used as such (when they are referred to as original charcoals in the text) as well as after out-gassing at 1110° in the manner described before.

Procedure : Five g. sample (oven-dried at 110°) was mixed with 500 ml. of chlorine water (~0.05 N) in one litre bottles wrapped in thick black papers and the suspension shaken mechanically for 24 hrs. The supernatant liquid was then decanted off and the volume made to one litre again on the addition of fresh chlorine water.

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2. B. R. Puri, O. P. Mahajan and D. D. Singh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 171.
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4. W. O. Stacy, G. Imperial and P. L. Walker, Jr., *Carbon*, 1966, 4, 343.
5. H. P. Bohm, U. Hofmann and A. Clauss, *Proc. Third Carbon Conf.*, Pergamon Press. p. 241 (1959).

The suspension was shaken again for the next 24 hrs. This process was repeated 12 times. The amount of oxygen chemisorbed after every alternative treatment was estimated by evacuating 1 g. portion in a resistance tube furnace heated gradually upto 1200°C and analysing the gases (CO_2 , CO and H_2O) evolved. The amount of chlorine chemisorbed simultaneously was estimated by heating separately 1 g. portion in a current of hydrogen at 800°C and estimating HCl evolved. Base adsorption capacity, as a measure of surface acidity, and bromine fixation capacity, as a measure of surface unsaturation, were determined by the methods used previously⁶.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amounts of oxygen and chlorine chemisorbed by the various samples of sugar and coconut charcoals, during some of the successive treatments with

Fig. 1 † Chemisorption of oxygen and chlorine by sugar charcoal on successive treatments with chlorine water.

chlorine water are plotted in figs. 1 and 2 respectively. It is seen that while oxygen and chlorine are chemisorbed simultaneously, the amount of oxygen chemisorbed in all samples except the original charcoals is greater than that of chlorine at all stages. In the case of the original charcoals also the amount of oxygen chemisorbed

Fig. 2. Chemisorption of oxygen and chlorine by coconut charcoal on successive treatments with chlorine water.

initially is greater than that of chlorine but later on the amount of chlorine chemisorbed exceeds that of oxygen, more so in coconut charcoals than in sugar charcoal. It appears that as charcoal is outgassed at increasing temperatures it gets activated for chemisorption of oxygen but deactivated for chemisorption of chlorine. It is highly likely that evacuation, while creating additional sites for fixation of oxygen, causes partial elimination of the sites where fixation of chlorine could be possible.

The maximum amounts of oxygen and chlorine fixed up ultimately after 12 treatments by the various samples of charcoal together with their initial hydrogen

contents obtained by micro-analysis are presented in table I. It is significant that the amount of chlorine fixed up by sugar or coconut charcoal decreases with fall in its hydrogen content. It appears highly probable that chlorine is fixed largely in replacement of combined hydrogen. However, since the amount of chlorine fixed is much less than that of hydrogen content of charcoal in every case, it appears that it is only the hydrogen present in the surface layer of charcoal which

TABLE I

Amounts of oxygen and chlorine chemisorbed by the various samples of sugar and coconut charcoals after 12 treatments with chlorine water.

Description of the sample	Initial hydrogen content (milliatoms/g)	Oxygen chemisorbed as (milliatoms/g)			Total oxygen chemisorbed (milliatoms/g)	Chlorine chemisorbed (milliatoms/g.)
		CO ₂	CO	H ₂ O		
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>						
Original		33.8	2.10	nil	2.47	3.23
Outgassed at	400°	33.0	1.94	0.32	2.64	2.62
" "	700	25.8	3.32	0.25	3.72	1.56
" "	1100	10.8	4.10	0.62	4.72	0.44
<i>Coconut charcoal</i>						
Original		22.3	2.35	0.05	2.40	3.62
Outgassed at	400°	20.1	2.38	0.08	2.73	2.69
" "	700	10.1	2.70	0.11	3.20	0.65
" "	1100	6.2	2.43	0.92	3.35	0.26

is replaceable by chlorine. The rest of the hydrogen held within the granules⁷ or minute capillary pores is not accessible to the much larger molecules of chlorine for the substitution reaction. In this connection it may be noted that coconut charcoal which is less porous and contains relatively coarser particles than sugar charcoal can fix more chlorine in spite of its relatively lower hydrogen content.

The amount of oxygen chemisorbed (which incidentally is disposed off mostly as CO₂) by sugar as well as coconut charcoal is seen to increase with increase in the temperature of evacuation. It is been shown earlier⁶ that certain unsaturated sites are created on evacuation. It appears highly likely that increase in the chemisorption of oxygen is due to its fixation at these sites. This view receives support from the fact that the amount of unsaturation (as measured by bromine value⁶ which increases with increase in the temperature of evacuation of charcoal (table II, col. 1) falls appreciably after treatment with chlorine water. However, decrease in surface unsaturation may as well be due to fixation of a part of the chlorine at these sites. It was thought of interest, therefore, to analyse the data further.

7. R. B. Anderson, and P. H. Emmet, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 753.

It has been shown⁸ that combined oxygen which comes off as carbon dioxide (CO₂-complex) is of two types : one acidic and titratable against alkalis and the other neutral. The second type of oxygen is fixed up at the unsaturated sites. In the case of original as well as 400°-outgassed sugar and coconut charcoals, increase in the amount of CO₂-complex formed is seen to be almost equivalent to increase in

TABLE II

Amounts of oxygen and chlorine fixed in relation to surface unsaturation

Description of the sample	Surface unsaturation (milliatoms of bromine/100 g.)		Increase in CO ₂ complex (m.e./100 g.)	Increase in base adsorption capacity (m.e./100.g)	Amount of neutral CO ₂ complex (m.e./100 g.) or amount of oxygen fixed at unsaturated sites (milliatoms/100 g.)	Chlorine fixed by addition	Total oxygen fixed	Total chlorine fixed
	Before treatment	After treatment	(m.e./100 g.)	(m.e./100.g)	(milliatoms/100 g.)			
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>								
Original	31	nil	210	206	nil	31	247	323
Outgassed at 400°	271	197	194	192	nil	74	264	262
„ „ 700	376	133	332	217	115	128	372	156
„ „ 1100	388	214	410	281	129	44	472	44
<i>Coconut charcoal</i>								
Original	38	28	235	237	nil	10	240	362
Outgassed at 400°	201	131	238	236	nil	70	273	269
„ „ 700	289	62	270	95	175	52	320	65
„ „ 1100	291	120	243	99	144	26	335	26

the base adsorption capacity, when expressed in similar units (col. 3 and 4). Therefore in these cases little or none of the oxygen is fixed up at the unsaturated sites. However, in the case of the 700°-and 1100°-outgassed charcoals increase in the amount of CO₂-complex formed is much more than increase in the base adsorption capacity, showing that in these cases some of the oxygen is added up at the unsaturated sites. The difference between the total amount of the CO₂-complex formed and base adsorption capacity can be taken, as before⁸, as the amount of the neutral complex formed or the amount of oxygen fixed at unsaturated sites. These values are included in table II. However, decrease in bromine value after treatment with chlorine water is seen to be greater than the amount of oxygen fixed at the unsaturated sites, as obtained above. It is evident, therefore, that some chlorine, accounting for the rest of the fall of surface unsaturation, is also fixed at these sites. Working on this basis, the amounts of oxygen and chlorine added up at the unsaturated sites could be calculated. These values are given in table II (col. 5 and 6). However, these values are less than the total amounts of oxygen and chlorine chemisorbed in most cases. Therefore, there must be certain other sites as well where oxygen and chlorine are

fixed. These sites for chlorine are provided by combined hydrogen along the surface, as already mentioned, while those for oxygen are provided by active centres where formation of quinonic and phenolic complexes (capable of evolving carbon monoxide and water) is possible or where fixation of two oxygen atoms per active surface carbon atom giving rise to acidic CO_2 -complex is possible⁸. Thus while there are certain common sites where fixation of both oxygen and chlorine can take place in competition with each other there are also certain other sites along charcoal surface where fixation of oxygen and chlorine can take place independently of each other.

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